

Pattern of Musculoskeletal Pain and Associated Factors among Small Scale Rice Farmers in Jigawa State, Nigeria

Kani Musa Zakari¹_{A-G}, O. Owoeye i²_{A-G}, C. B aiyejunsule²_{A-G}, M.U. Badaru¹_{A-G},
Y.U. Mahmoud¹_{A-G}

¹Department of Physiotherapy, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria

²Department of Physiotherapy, College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Nigeria

Received: May 02.2016; Accepted: May 29.2016

Abstract

Introduction: Farming could predispose an individual to developing musculoskeletal pain (MSP). This study investigated the pattern of MSP and associated factors among small scale rice farmers in Jigawa State.

Materials and Methods: In this cross-sectional survey, 552 peasant rice farmers were purposefully recruited from three Local Government Areas of Jigawa State, Nigeria. MSP was assessed with Standardized Nordic Questionnaire (Modified). The associations between MSP, work related factors and demographic characteristics of participants were analysed with Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests at significance level of 0.05

Result: Low back and knee joints pains were the most commonly reported MSP. Association exist between gender and each of hip joint pain ($P < 0.05$) and elbow joint pain ($P < 0.05$). There was association between neck pain and prolong daily hours of rice farming ($P < 0.05$). Age and years of farming have no association with MSP ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Low back pain is common among rice farmers in Jigawa State. Prolong daily hours of rice farming is associated with development of MSP.

Keywords: Musculoskeletal Pain, Rice, Farmers

Introduction

Farming is generally perceived by both farmers and the general public as a healthy outdoor activity; however it could sometimes be hazardous and can presents a range of threats to the farmers' health.[1] Because of the nature of farm work, farmers are at risk of developing musculoskeletal pain (MSP).[2] MSP affects the musculoskeletal system including the nerves, tendons, muscles and supporting structures such as the intervertebral disc.[3]

The pattern of MSP has been documented in different occupational groups in Nigeria.[4] A survey of MSP among computer users in Nigeria by Adedoyin et al[5] reported the prevalence of low back pain and neck pain to be 74% and 73% respectively. Furthermore, Udoe and Aguwa[6] reported that low back pain and neck pain are the most common MSP among dentists in South-eastern Nigeria. Also, Adegoke, et al [7] reported low back pain and neck pain as the most common type of MSP among physiotherapists. The 12 months prevalence of low back pain among staff in a rural hospital and office workers in an urban centre in Nigeria was reported to be 46% and 38% respectively[8,9]. There is however dearth of studies that

assess musculoskeletal pain among peasant rice farmers in Nigeria.

Furthermore, most farmers in rural communities in Nigeria are engaged in non-mechanized farming that is usually tedious and laborious and coupled with use of unimproved and uncomfortable farming techniques and tools, it is important to assess the pattern of MSP among them. This is of great concern to all health care professionals dealing with the management of pain, especially the physiotherapists. Hence, this study is designed to evaluate the pattern of MSP and associated factors among small scale rice farmers in Jigawa State.

Materials and Methods

The cross-sectional study recruited small scale rice farmers from the 3 major rice producing Local Government Areas of Jigawa State using purposive sampling method and these include Auyo, Hadejia, and Guri Local Government Areas. The inclusion criteria are being a peasant or small scale rice farmer, age between 25 and 50 years and a member of Jigawa State rice farmers association.

Farmers with known reported orthopaedic or neurological problems that were not directly related to peasant rice farming such as trauma, infections, falls, assaults and road traffic accidents were however, excluded from the study.

Ethical consideration

The protocol of this study was approved by the Research and Ethics Committee of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital, Idi-Araba, Lagos State Nigeria.

Data collection procedure

A letter of introduction from the Department of Physiotherapy, University of Lagos, was taken to the rice farmers associations of the local government areas under the study. Thereafter, the farmers were met in groups during their various meeting times while other farmers were met

individually. The aim and objectives of the research were fully explained to the participating farmers and their cooperation was highly solicited for. Thereafter, copies of the research questionnaires were distributed to most of them and it was directly administered on those who are not literate in English language. Those who received the questionnaire were asked to fill and return it back.

Assessment musculoskeletal pain

MSP was assessed with modified Nordic questionnaire by Kuorinko et al.[10] Nordic questionnaires have excellent sensitivity in all situations (82.3%-100%).[11] The original Standardized Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire has moderate correlation with Oswestry disability index (R= 0.479 p < 0.01) and good internal consistency of $\alpha=0.86$. [12]

Table 1: Demographic and work-related characteristics of the rice farmers N = number of the participants (frequency); %=percentage

Variable	n	Minimum (Years)	Maximum	Mean (Years)	Std. Deviation
Age	552	10	46	32.08	5.853
Years of farming	552	2	14	5.22	2.454
Number of hours	552	2	16	7.82	3.015
Gender	n	%			
Female	49	8.9			
Male	503	91.1			
Total	552	100.0			
Age group (Years)	n	%			
Less than 20	10	1.8			
21-30	255	46.2			
31-40	227	41.1			
41-50	60	10.9			
Total	552	100.0			
Year of farming	n	%			
1-5 years	318	57.6			
6-10 years	221	40.0			
11 years and above	13	2.4			
Total	552	100.0			
Hours of work	n	%			
1-4 hours	85	15.4			
5-8 hours	218	39.5			
Above 8 hours	249	45.1			
Total	552	100.0			
Work status	n	%			
Full time	424	76.8			
Part time	128	23.2			

Figure 1: Pattern and distributions musculoskeletal pain among rice farmers. Body Parts of participants

The modified questionnaire consists of two sections: The first section enquire about age category of the rice farmers, gender, farming status (part time or full time), years of farming experience, daily hours spent doing farming and other questions regarding the routine farming activities. In the second part of the questionnaire, a diagram showing 10 different anatomical body areas was used for illustrative purpose to help farmers in answering questions relating to work-related MSP affecting specific parts of their bodies within the last 12 months.

Parts of the body shown on the diagram included neck, shoulders, upper back, Elbow/forearm, low back, wrist/hands, thumb, hip/highs, knees, and ankle/feet. They were then asked to fill a table by ticking the boxes corresponding to the body areas they had a work-related MSP or discomfort during the last 12 months and to indicate the kind of treatment (if any) they sought in the relevant box.

Data analysis

The data obtained were summarized with descriptive statistics and analysed with inferential statistics of Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests using SPSS version 18.0. Fisher's exact test was used when any of the items of Chi-square table is less than five. Chi-square analysis was used when all the items of Chi-square table are greater than or equal to 5. The alpha level of significant was set at 0.05.

Results

Five hundred and fifty two (552) small scale rice farmers from three Local Government Areas of Jigawa State participated in this study. Majority of them 503(91.1%) were males who are predominantly within the age ranges of 21-40 years 482(87.3%) and full time rice farmers 424 (76.8%). More than half of them 318(57.6%) had 1 to 5 years of farming experience and many of them 249(45.1%) work for more than eight daily hours in their farms as shown in table 1 (Tab.1).

Work-related musculoskeletal pain among participants

In this study, Low back (41.8%) and knee joint (17.5%) were the body parts mostly affected. However, MSP of wrist (0.5%) and thumb (0.5%) were the least reported anatomical body sites as presented in figure 1 (Fig. 1).

Association between musculoskeletal pain and work-related characteristics of the study participants

In this study there was significant association between gender and hip pain ($P < 0.05$) and between gender and elbow pain ($P < 0.05$) table 2 (Tab.2). There was no significant association between MSP and each of age groups ($P > 0.05$) table 3 and years of rice farming experience ($P > 0.05$) table 4. Finally, there was significant association between neck pain and daily hours of rice farming ($P < 0.05$), table 5 (Tab. 3, 4, 5).

Table 2: Association between musculoskeletal pains and gender of the rice farmers (N=552) * Significant N=number of participants; freq=frequency; X²= chi-square

	Female		Male		Total	Fishers exact /X ²	P value
	Freq	%	Freq	%			
Ankle pain							
Yes	0	0.0	27	5.4	27	1.732	0.1570
No	49	100.0	476	94.6	525		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Hip pain							
Yes	13	26.5	62	12.3	75	6.511	0.0107*
No	36	73.5	441	87.7	477		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Elbow pain							
Yes	2	4.1	38	7.6	40	14.839	0.0001*
No	47	95.9	465	92.4	512		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Knee pain							
Yes	4	8.2	91	18.1	95	2.431	0.1189
No	45	91.8	412	81.9	457		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Low back pain							
Yes	21	42.9	210	41.7	231	0.000	0.9987
No	28	57.1	293	58.3	321		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Neck pain							
Yes	5	10.2	37	7.4	42	0.190	0.6631
No	44	89.8	466	92.6	510		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Shoulder pain							
Yes	0	0.0	9	1.8	9	0.125	0.7239
No	49	100.0	494	98.2	543		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
Thumb pain							
Yes	0	0.0	3	0.6	3	0.226	0.6343
No	49	100.0	500	99.4	549		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
upper back pain							
Yes	4	8.2	23	4.6	27	0.586	0.4440
No	45	91.8	480	95.4	525		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		
wrist pain							
Yes	0	0.0	3	0.6	3	0.226	1.0000
No	49	100.0	500	99.4	549		
Total	49	100.0	503	100.0	552		

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the pattern of musculoskeletal pain (MSP) and associated factors among small scale rice farmers in Jigawa State, Nigeria. In this study majority of the rice farmers were males and most of them were young adults with average age less than 35years

The preponderance of male over female farmers could probably be due to the fact that males were generally regarded as bread winners in Jigawa State, as such they had to work and feed their families.

More so, subsistence farming especially in the rural areas is generally non-mechanized and involves a lot of hard manual labour that the very young and old may find it difficult to do, hence the reason why young adults were the predominant age group involved in subsistence farming.

These findings were however in contrast with those of Keawduangdee et al,[13] and Luangwilai et al,[14] where the average ages of rice farmers in both studies were more than 44 years. This implies that the average rice

farmer in Jigawa state is young and probably less experienced in rice farming.

Additionally, the outcome of this study shows that, more than three quarter of the participants were full time rice farmers. The possible reason could be because peasant farming is the major occupation of most of the rural population in the state.

Furthermore, this study observed that most of the peasant rice farmers work for more than eight hours daily on their farms. This implies that majority of the rice farmers spent most of their daily hours in the farms.

This latter finding corroborates that of Keawduangdee et al, [13] where majority of the rice farmer worked in the field 7 hours or more per day.

In this study, back pain is the most frequently reported MSP among peasant rice farmers. This finding is in line with that of Keawduangdee et al,[13] and different from that of Luangwilai et al, [14] who reported shoulder pain as the most reported MSP among rice farmers.[14]

The possible reason for the difference in outcome between this study and that of Luangwilai et al,[14] could be because the young and less experienced farmers in this study could be unaware of important areas of exposure to risks of developing MSP associated with rice farming compared to the older and probably more experience farmers in the study by Luangwilai et al. [14]

Table 3: Association between musculoskeletal pain and age of rice farmers (n=552). N=number of participants; freq=frequency; X²=chi-square; yrs= years

	Age (yrs)				Total	Fishers' exact/ X ²	P value
	≤40yrs		>40yrs				
	Freq	%	Freq	%			
Ankle pain							
Yes	9	3.4	18	6.3	27	1.870	0.1715
No	256	96.6	269	93.7	525		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Hip pain							
Yes	21	7.9	19	6.6	40	0.182	0.6699
No	244	92.1	268	93.4	512		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Elbow pain							
Yes	38	14.3	37	12.9	75	0.006	0.9359
No	227	85.7	250	87.1	477		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Knee pain							
Yes	47	17.7	48	16.7	95	0.041	0.8403
No	218	82.3	239	83.3	457		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Low back pain							
Yes	112	42.3	119	41.5	231	0.011	0.9170
No	153	57.7	168	58.5	321		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Neck pain							
Yes	21	7.9	21	7.3	42	0.012	0.9138
No	244	92.1	266	92.7	510		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Shoulder pain							
Yes	5	1.9	4	1.4	9	0.015	0.9040
No	260	98.1	283	98.6	543		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
Thumb pain							
Yes	0	0.0	3	1.0	3	1.187	0.2759
No	265	100.0	284	99.0	549		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
upper back pain							
Yes	11	4.2	16	5.6	27	0.333	0.5636
No	254	95.8	271	94.4	525		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		
wrist pain							
Yes	1	0.4	2	0.7	3	0.005	0.9448
No	264	99.6	285	99.3	549		
Total	265	100.0	287	100.0	552		

Furthermore, back pain the most commonly reported MSP among Nigerians workers.[4,6,7] For example, Adegoke et al [7] found that back pain was the most common work related musculoskeletal disorder among Nigerian physiotherapists. Similar results were obtained by Udoye et al [6] and Adedoyin et al [5] on the preponderance of back pain among dentists and computer users in Nigeria respectively.

The possible reason why back pain was the most reported MSP among peasant rice farmer is that non-mechanized farming requires prolonged bending of the trunk. [4]

Furthermore, the observation that knee joint pain, was the second most commonly reported MSP was in line with the finding of Swangnetr et al,[15] and Karukunchit et al, [16] who reported that rice farming leads significant lower limb pain and malalignment respectively.

In this study significant association was observed between gender and hip pain. Higher percentage of the females reported having hip pain when compared with the percentage of male with hip pain. This implies that female rice farmers are more prone to having hip pain than their male counterparts in Jigawa state.

Furthermore significant association exist between gender and elbow pain. Higher percentage of male rice farmers encountered elbow pain when compared with the percentage of female rice farmers with elbow pain. This implies that male rice farmers are more disposed to having elbow pain than their male counterparts Jigawa state.

Table 4: Association between Musculoskeletal pain and years of farming. N=number of the participants. freq=frequency

	years of farming				Total	Fishers' exact / X ²	P value
	≤10yrs		>10yrs				
	Freq	%	Freq	%			
Ankle pain							
Yes	25	4.6	2	15.4	27	1.265	0.2608
No	514	95.4	11	84.6	525		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Hip pain							
Yes	39	7.2	1	7.7	40	0.229	0.6323
No	500	92.8	12	92.3	512		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Elbow pain							
Yes	73	13.5	2	15.4	75	0.048	0.8273
No	466	86.5	11	84.6	477		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Knee pain							
Yes	93	17.3	2	15.4	95	0.038	0.8451
No	446	82.7	11	84.6	457		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Low back pain							
Yes	228	42.3	3	23.1	231	1.219	0.2696
No	311	57.7	10	76.9	321		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Neck pain							
Yes	40	7.4	2	15.4	42	0.292	0.5886
No	499	92.6	11	84.6	510		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Shoulder pain							
Yes	9	1.7	0	0.0	9	1.171	0.2793
No	530	98.3	13	100.0	543		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
Thumb pain							
Yes	3	0.6	0	0.0	3	2.687	0.1012
No	536	99.4	13	100.0	549		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
upper back pain							
Yes	26	4.8	1	7.7	27	0.031	0.8597
No	513	95.2	12	92.3	525		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		
wrist pain							
Yes	3	0.6	0	0.0	3	2.687	0.1012
No	536	99.4	13	100.0	549		
Total	539	100.0	13	100.0	552		

Further results in this study showed that there was negligible association between MSP and years of rice farming experience. The result is supported by the report of Campo et al,[17] The possible reason for the insignificant association observed in this study between musculoskeletal pain and years of farming could probably be because more than half of the respondents have only few (1-5) years of farming experience. Finally, the significant association that exist between neck pain and daily hours of rice farming means that the number of daily hour spent doing rice farming might have link with the development of neck pain. In this study neck pain was more reported by farmers who spent more than 8 hours daily on the farm.

Conclusion

Low back pain is common among rice farmers in Jigawa state. Prolong daily hours of rice farming is associated with development of MSP

Recommendations

- Peasant farmers in Jigawa state should be introduced to modern farming techniques that do not require the use of heavy manual labour and if very expensive, farmers can be help in their small groups.
- Different programmes on coping strategies should be organised for those farmers with musculoskeletal pain/discomfort as this will help them to understand their condition and how to cope with it.
- Further study should identify which of the process of rice farming mostly cause MSP by analysing difficulties involved in all stages of field preparation, rice planting, transplanting, weeding and harvesting.

References:

1. Lewis MQ, Sprince NL, Burmeister LF, Whitten PS, Zewerling C. Work related injuries among Iowa farm family, health and hazard. Surveillance project. *Am J Ind Med*, 1998; 33: 510-517.
2. Walker-Bone K, Palmer KT. Musculoskeletal disorders in farmers and farm workers. *Occup Med (London)*. 2002; 52:441-450.
3. Woolf AD, Pfleger B. Burden of major musculoskeletal conditions. *Bull. WHO*. 2003; 81:646-656.
4. Akinpelu OA, Adesola CO, Akinwoye SO. Prevalence and pattern of musculoskeletal pain in rural community in south western Nigeria. *The International Journal of Epidemiology*. 2010; 8(2).
5. Adedoyin RA, Idowu BO, Adegunodo RE, Idowu PA. Muscle pain associated with the use of computer system in Nigeria. *Internet Journal of Pain, System Control and Palliative Care*2004.
6. Udoye CI, Aguwa EN. Musculoskeletal symptoms, a survey among selected Nigerian dentists. *International Journal of Dental Science*. 2007; 5:1.
7. Adegoke BOA, Akodu AK, Oyeyemi AL. Work related musculoskeletal disorders among Nigerian physiotherapists. *Musculoskeletal disorders*. 2008; 9:112.
8. Omokhodion FO, Sanya AO. Risk factors for low back pain among office workers in Ibadan, Southwest Nigeria. *Occupational Medicine*. 2003; 53 (4):287-289.
9. Omokhodion FO, Umar SR, Ogunowo BE. Prevalence of low back pain among staff in a rural hospital in Nigeria. *Occupational Medicine*. 2000; 50: 107-110.
10. Kuorinko L, Jonsson B, Kilbon A. Standardized Nordic questionnaire for the analysis of musculoskeletal pain. *Clinical anatomy* 1987; 17:21-5
11. Descatha A, Roquelaure Y, Chastang J.F., Evanoff B, Melchior M., Mariot CHaC., Imbernon E., Goldberg M., Leclerc A. Validity of Nordic-style questionnaires in the surveillance of upper-limb work-related musculoskeletal disorders. *Scand J Work Environ Health* 2007; 33:58-65.
12. Mesquita CC., Ribeiro JC., Moreira P. Portuguese version of the standardized Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire: cross cultural and reliability. *Int J Public Health* 18 (2010), 5, pp. 461-466. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10389-010-0331-0>
13. Keawduangdee P., Puntumetakul R., Swangnetr M., Laohasiriwong W., Settheetham D., Yamauchi J., and Boucaut R.. Prevalence of low back pain and associated factors among farmers during the rice transplanting process. *J Phys Ther Sci*. 2015; 27(7): 2239-2245.
14. Luangwilai T., Norkaew S., Siriwong W. Factors associated with musculoskeletal disorders among rice farmers: cross sectional study in Tarnlalord sub-district, Phimai district, Nakhonratchasima province, Thailand. *J Health Res*. 2014; 28(Suppl.): S85-S91
15. Swangnetr M., Kaber DB., Puntumetakul R., Gross MT. Ergonomics-related risk identification and pain analysis for farmers involved in rice field preparation. *Work*. 2014;49(1):63-71. doi: 10.3233/WOR-131768.
16. Karukunchit U., Puntumetakul R., Swangnetr M., Boucaut R. Prevalence and risk factor analysis of lower extremity abnormal alignment characteristics among rice farmers. *Dove Medical Press Limited*. 2015: 785-795 doi <http://dx.doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S81898>
17. Campo M., Weiser S., Koenig KI, Nordin M. Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders in Physical Therapists: A prospective cohort study with 1-Year follow-up. *Phy Ther* 2008; 88(5): 608-619.

Correspondence address

Zakari Kani Musa
 Department of Physiotherapy,
 Faculty of Allied Health Sciences,
 Bayero University Kano, Nigeria.
 Email: musakanizakari@yahoo.com
 Mobile: +2348054922262

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.

Table 5: Association between musculoskeletal pain and daily hours of farming (n=552) N= number of the participant; *Significant; freq=frequency; X2= Chi-square; hrs=hours

	hours of work				Total	Fishers' exact / X ²	value
	≤8hrs		Above 8 hrs				
	Freq	%	Freq	%			
Ankle pain							
Yes	17	5.6	10	4.0	27	0.444	0.5054
No	286	94.4	239	96.0	525		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Hip pain							
Yes	28	9.2	12	4.8	40	3.345	0.0674
No	275	90.8	237	95.2	512		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Elbow pain							
Yes	37	12.2	38	15.3	75	0.839	0.3598
No	266	87.8	211	84.7	477		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Knee pain							
Yes	58	19.1	37	14.9	95	1.472	0.2251
No	245	80.9	212	85.1	457		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Low back pain							
Yes	116	38.3	115	46.2	231	3.189	0.0741
No	187	61.7	134	53.8	321		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Neck pain							
Yes	24	7.9	42	16.9	42	9.560	0.0020*
No	279	92.1	207	83.1	510		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Shoulder pain							
Yes	4	1.3	5	2.0	9	0.088	0.7662
No	299	98.7	244	98.0	543		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
Thumb pain							
Yes	1	0.3	2	0.8	3	0.029	0.8644
No	302	99.7	247	99.2	549		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
upper back pain							
Yes	15	5.0	12	4.8	27	0.016	0.8988
No	288	95.0	237	95.2	525		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		
wrist pain							
Yes	3	1.0	0	0.0	3	0.985	0.3209
No	300	99.0	249	100.0	549		
Total	303	100.0	249	100.0	552		